

Synthesis, spectral, thermal, catalytic and biological studies of some transition metal complexes with unsymmetrical Schiff base ligand

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Abstract : Complexes of VO^{IV} , Cr^{III} , Mn^{III} , Fe^{III} , Zr^{IV} , MoO_2^{VI} , WO_2^{VI} and UO_2^{VI} with an unsymmetrical tetradentate Schiff base ligand derived from 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone, 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitroacetophenone and carbonylhydrazide have been prepared. All the complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, UV-Vis and IR spectroscopy, magnetic measurements and thermal analysis. The complexes were found to be quite stable and decomposition of the complexes ended with respective metal oxides as an end product. The IR spectral data suggest that the ligand behaves as a dibasic tetradentate ligand with ONNO donor atoms sequence towards central metal ion. The solid-state electrical conductivity has been measured over 313–403 K temperature range and all the compounds showed semiconducting behavior as their conductivity increases with increase in temperature. The powder XRD study of VO^{IV} complex suggests the triclinic crystal system to the complex. The VO^{IV} and Mn^{III} complexes have been tested for the catalytic oxidation of styrene. The ligand and its some of the complexes have also been screened for their antimicrobial activity using various micro-organisms and all of them were found to be moderately active against the organisms.

Keywords : Unsymmetrical Schiff base, complexes, d.c. conductivity, TGA, XRD, catalytic activity, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Schiff bases have played a special role as chelating ligands in main group and transition metal coordination chemistry because of their stability under a variety of redox conditions and because of imine ligands are borderline Lewis bases. Schiff bases ligands and their metal complexes find applications in the fields of food and dyes industry, agriculture, analytical chemistry catalysis, polymer sciences, biological science as antimicrobial agents, medical science as anticancer and metal corrosion inhibition agents¹⁻⁴. Unsymmetrical complexes are very important in biological process systems as well as in industrial catalysis and are interesting also from theoretical point of view⁵⁻⁷. A large number of publications describing the preparation of the unsymmetrical ligand have been reported and very little work has been reported on complexes with higher valent metal ions with the unsymmetrical tetradentate Schiff base^{8,9}. However, the complexes involving Schiff base ligand synthesized from 2-hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone, 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-3-nitroacetophenone and carbonylhydrazide involving tri-, tetra- and

hexavalent metal ions have not been synthesized as yet, therefore, it was thought of interest to synthesize unsymmetrical Schiff base ligand derived from 2-hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone, 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-3-nitroacetophenone and carbonylhydrazide and its metal complexes with tri-, tetra- and hexavalent metal ions and characterized by various physicochemical methods. X-Ray diffraction study of VO^{IV} complex has been carried out and some representative complexes have been tested towards catalytic oxidation of styrene. The ligand and its some complexes have also been screened for their microorganism activities.

Results and discussion

The analytical data for the ligand and complexes is given in Table 1 and agreed with their proposed formulae. The complexes are coloured and insoluble in water and common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in DMF and DMSO. They are non-hygroscopic, highly stable under normal conditions and all of them decompose at higher temperature.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of ligand and its complexes

Sr. no.	Compd.	Formula weight (g mol ⁻¹)	Colour	Elemental analyses (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Electrical conductivity σ (Ω^{-1} cm ⁻¹) at 373 K	Activation energy (eV)
				C	H	N	M		
1.	H ₂ L	399.40	Ivory	56.91 (57.14)	4.95 (5.30)	17.20 (17.53)	-	-	
2.	[VOL].H ₂ O	482.34	Pine	47.25 (47.31)	4.23 (4.39)	14.14 (14.52)	9.97 (10.56)	3.36 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	0.9738
3.	[CrL.H ₂ O.Cl].H ₂ O	520.86	Burnt umber	42.91 (43.81)	4.12 (4.45)	12.88 (13.45)	9.08 (9.98)	5.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.4372
4.	[MnL.OAc]	511.36	Light brown	49.17 (49.32)	3.83 (4.34)	13.08 (13.70)	9.97 (10.74)	2.22 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.6170
5.	[FeL.H ₂ O.Cl].H ₂ O	524.71	Burnt seinna	42.72 (43.49)	4.26 (4.42)	13.10 (13.35)	9.98 (10.64)	7.79 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.7247
6.	[ZrL(OH) ₂ .H ₂ O].H ₂ O	558.65	Putty	39.09 (40.85)	4.33 (4.51)	11.87 (12.54)	15.93 (16.33)	1.10 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.6395
7.	[MoO ₂ L]	525.32	Dark evergreen	43.11 (43.44)	2.77 (3.65)	12.86 (13.33)	17.79 (18.26)	4.73 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.8148
8.	[WO ₂ L.NCS]	671.30	Chartreuse	33.64 (35.78)	2.42 (2.85)	12.13 (12.52)	26.73 (27.39)	5.37 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.8107
9.	[UO ₂ L]	667.41	Umber	33.80 (34.19)	2.68 (2.87)	9.92 (10.49)	34.99 (35.66)	1.47 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.6304

Table 2. Thermal decomposition, magnetic properties and electronic spectral data of ligand and its complexes

Sr. no.	Compd.	m.p.*/Half decomposition temp. (°C)	Activation energy (kJ mol ⁻¹)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Electronic spectra	
					Absorption band (nm)	Assignment
1.	H ₂ L	312	41.681	-	-	-
2.	[VOL].H ₂ O	410	23.618	1.52	923 520 385	$d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{xy}d_{yz}(e^*)$ $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}(b_1^*)$ $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{z^2}(a_1^*)$
3.	[CrL.H ₂ O.Cl].H ₂ O	384	23.564	3.84	618 480 281	${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$
4.	[MnL.OAc]	376	37.139	4.84	746 614 515 359	${}^5B_1 \rightarrow {}^5B_2$ ${}^5B_1 \rightarrow {}^5A_1$ ${}^5B_1 \rightarrow {}^5E$ LMCT
5.	[FeL.H ₂ O.Cl].H ₂ O	342	25.383	5.73	764 642 443	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$
6.	[ZrL(OH) ₂ .H ₂ O].H ₂ O	436	21.676	Diamagnetic	-	-
7.	[MoO ₂ L]	362	31.541	Diamagnetic	-	-
8.	[WO ₂ L.NCS]	374	32.408	Diamagnetic	-	-
9.	[UO ₂ L]	312	33.069	Diamagnetic	-	-

IR spectra :

The IR data of the spectra of ligand and its complexes are listed in Table 3. The IR spectra of the complexes are compared with those of the free ligand in order to determine the coordination sites that may involve in chelation. The IR spectrum of the free ligand shows a medium broad band at 2993 cm^{-1} due to intramolecular hydrogen bonded phenolic νOH group. The absence of this band in the spectra of metal complexes indicates the breaking of hydrogen bond and coordination of phenolic oxygen to the metal after deprotonation¹⁰. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ phenolic stretching frequency appeared at 1258 cm^{-1} in the ligand get shifted to higher wave number at 1259–1280 cm^{-1} in spectra of complexes, also suggest the coordination of ligand through phenolic oxygen via deprotonation¹¹. The IR spectrum of ligand shows a strong band at 1639 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretch. On complexation this band shifted to lower frequency values in all complexes by 4–49 cm^{-1} . It indicates that the azomethine nitrogen is coordinated to the metal ion^{12–14}. The $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ bands of the ligand at 3262 and 1713 cm^{-1} do not change their positions after complexation, indicating that ligand exist in keto form in free state as well as in all the complexes¹⁵. Non involvement of amido oxygen in coordination of the acetate group in Mn^{III} complexes is confirmed due to difference between the two bands ($\Delta\nu > 191 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) appeared at 1611 and 1420 cm^{-1} which are assignable to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ modes. A band at 667 cm^{-1} due to $\delta(\text{O}-\text{C}-\text{O})$ which is confirmed a diag-

nostic band for a monodentate ligand^{16,17}. The coordination of water in VO^{IV} , Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} complexes are indicated by the appearance of bands at 3375–3428, 1579–1683, 849–878 and 743–862 cm^{-1} assignable to $\gamma(\text{O}-\text{H})$, $\delta(\text{O}-\text{H})$, $\rho_{\text{t}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ and $\rho_{\text{w}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ modes respectively¹⁸. The MoO_2^{VI} , UO_2^{VI} , WO_2^{VI} complexes show new bands around 951, 970, 944 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$, $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ and $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{O}=\text{W}=\text{O})$ vibrations¹⁹. The VO^{IV} and Zr^{IV} complexes show new bands at around 975 and 1133 cm^{-1} respectively due to $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ and $\delta(\text{Zr}-\text{OH})$ vibrations. The WO_2^{VI} complex shows bands around 2073 (CN), 786 (CS) and 479 cm^{-1} (NCS) suggesting that the thiocyanate group act as ligand in which bonding through nitrogen takes place²⁰.

Electronic spectra :

The magnetic and electronic spectral data are given in Table 2. The electronic spectrum of VO^{IV} complex shows absorption bands at 923, 520 and 385 nm corresponding to square pyramidal geometry²¹, these bands may be assigned to $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{xy}d_{yz}(e^*)$, $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}(b_1^*)$ and $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{z^2}(a_1^*)$, transitions, respectively²¹. The Cr^{III} complex shows absorption bands at 618, 480 and 281 nm due to ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, transitions, indicating an octahedral geometry around the Cr^{III} ion²². The reflectance spectral parameters for Cr^{III} are found to be $Dq = 1618.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 525 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.571$ and % covalency = 42.9. B value is found to be considerably lower than that of the free ion value suggesting a considerable amount of

Table 3. IR data (cm^{-1}) of ligand and its complexes

Sr. no.	Ligand/Complex	Phenolic O-H	N-H	C=N	C=O	C-O	N-N	M-O	M-N	H ₂ O
1.	H ₂ L	2993	3263	1639	1713	1258	1015	-	-	-
2.	[VOL].H ₂ O	-	3289	1636	1690	1272	1026	557	461	3383, 1683
3.	[CrL.H ₂ O.Cl].H ₂ O	-	3260	1617	1672	1252	1031	521	467	3383, 1620, 878, 743
4.	[MnL.OAc]	-	3269	1614	1733	1275	1029	542	425	-
5.	[FeL.H ₂ O.Cl].H ₂ O	-	3241	1597	1688	1259	1036	512	447	3375, 1614, 849, 762
6.	[ZrL(OH) ₂ .H ₂ O].H ₂ O	-	3280	1627	1667	1265	1022	569	413	3428, 1579, 862
7.	[MoO ₂ L]	-	3273	1590	1681	1277	1020	536	425	-
8.	[WO ₂ L.NCS]	-	3267	1594	1710	1268	1036	543	428	-
9.	[UO ₂ L]	-	3272	1627	1689	1280	1008	564	438	-

covalent character of the bond. The Mn^{III} complex shows absorption bands at 746, 614, 515 and 359 nm due to ${}^5B_1 \rightarrow {}^5B_2$, ${}^5B_1 \rightarrow {}^5A_1$ and ${}^5B_1 \rightarrow {}^5E$ and LMCT, transitions, corresponding to square pyramidal geometry of complex²³. The Fe^{III} complex shows absorption band at 764, 642 and 443 nm due to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, transitions, respectively towards octahedral geometry for the complex.

Magnetic properties :

The molar magnetic susceptibility of the VO^{IV} , Cr^{III} , Mn^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes at room temperature is given in Table 2. The μ_{eff} value of VO^{IV} , Cr^{III} , Mn^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes at room temperature are found to be 1.52, 3.84, 4.83 and 5.73 B.M respectively and which are lies in the range of the literature values^{23,24}. The Zr^{IV} , MoO_2^{VI} , WO_2^{VI} and UO_2^{VI} complexes are diamagnetic as expected from their electronic configuration.

Electrical conductivity measurements :

The solid state d.c. electrical conductivity of the complexes is given in Table 1. The solid state d.c. electrical conductivity was measured using pelleted material from 313–403 K. The solid state d.c. electrical conductivity increases with increases in the temperature²³. The electrical conductivity (σ) was found to vary according to the relation $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp (-E_a/kT)$ where σ_0 is a constant, E_a is the activation energy of electrical conduction, T is the absolute temperature and k is Boltzmann constant. The

solid state conductivity measurements show that the plot of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ are found to be linear over studied temperature ranged which indicates their semiconducting nature²⁶. The activation energy of electrical conductance lies in the range 3.36×10^{-10} to 5.95×10^{-4} eV.

Oxidation of styrene :

In generally, the catalytic oxidation of styrene gives the products like styrene oxide, benzaldehyde, benzoic acid, phenyl acetic acid and 1-phenyl ethane-1,2-diol and other side products²⁷. In the present study oxidation of styrene catalysed by the VO^{IV} and Mn^{III} complexes was carried out. The catalytic activity of these complexes was checked as a function of the amount of catalyst and oxidant H_2O_2 used. The amount of catalyst was used 0.020, 0.030 and 0.040 g respectively; amount of styrene and H_2O_2 (1 : 2) was fixed in presence of acetonitrile at 80 °C. The conversion of styrene in VO^{IV} and Mn^{III} complexes was found to be 16–27.8% and 8.5–24% respectively as shown in Figs. 2 and 3. The conversion of styrene increases with increase in amount of catalyst in presence of fixed amount of H_2O_2 and styrene.

Thermogravimetric study :

In order to know the presence of water molecules and decomposition pattern of complexes TG analysis have been carried out The thermograms reveals three stage decomposition pattern for Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} complexes and two stage decomposition patterns for VO^{IV} , Mn^{III} ,

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of synthesis of ligand (H₂L).

Fig. 2. Effect of VO^{IV} complex catalyst on % styrene conversion.

Fig. 3. Effect of Mn^{III} complex catalyst on % styrene conversion.

MoO₂^{VI}, WO₂^{VI} and UO₂^{VI} complexes. The TG curve of VO^{IV}, Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} complexes show elimination of a water molecule takes place between 70–120 °C indicating the presence of these water as lattice water molecules whereas water eliminated in between 145–230 °C indicating the presence of an coordinated water molecule in the complexes^{28–30} [% wt. loss, obs./calcd. VO^{IV} : 4.02/

3.73; Fe^{III} : 3.79/3.43 and Zr^{IV} : 3.48/3.22 for lattice water and Fe^{III} : 3.72/3.43 and Zr^{IV} : 3.64/3.22 for coordinated water]. The thermogram of Mn^{III} complex is almost stable up to 200 °C and then shows a gradual weight loss up to ~280 °C corresponding to loss of one acetate group. MoO₂^{VI}, WO₂^{VI} and UO₂^{VI} complexes are almost stable up to 160 °C indicating that absence of

any lattice or coordinated water molecules. The WO_2^{VI} complex shows weight loss in the range 170–222 °C which corresponds to loss of one thiocyanato group²⁰. The Broido method has been used to calculate thermal activation energy³¹ and values are given in Table 2. Finally stable metal oxide has been formed with an aerial oxidation of the complexes.

The representative Cr^{III} was chosen for DTA study. In the thermogram of Cr^{III} complex, the first step shows a steep slope between 85–110 °C with a mass loss of 3.82% (Calcd. 3.45%) indicates the removal of lattice water, an endothermic peak in the range 85–110 °C ($\Delta T_{\text{min}} = 95$ °C) in DTA corresponds to a dehydration step. In second step loss is takes place between 155–215 °C with

mass loss of 3.93% (Calcd. 3.45%) indicates the removal of coordinated water, an endothermic peak in the range 155–215 °C ($\Delta T_{\text{max}} = 180$ °C) in DTA analysis corresponds to loss of coordinated water. In third step rapid loss of weight between 280–390 °C due to quantitative elimination of ligand followed by gradual weight loss of up to 650 °C due to complete decomposition of coordinated part of ligand i.e. thermal degradation of ligand, a broad endotherm is observed in DTA, afterward the weight loss remained constant corresponding to stable metal oxide of Cr metal 12.24% (Calcd. 11.96%).

Powder XRD study :

The X-ray diffractogram of VO^{IV} complex has been studied as representative system (Fig. 4). The complex

Fig. 4. X-Ray diffraction spectrum of VO^{IV} complex.

Table 4. The parameters of unit cell and observed and calculated X-ray diffraction data of VO^{IV} complex

System : Triclinic $a = 7.5593 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 6.0199 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 5.9357 \text{ \AA}$ $\alpha = 95.557^\circ$ $\beta = 100.824^\circ$ $\gamma = 96.086^\circ$ $V = 261.92 \text{ \AA}^3$						
Peak no.	d (Obsd.)	d (Calcd.)	2θ (Obsd.)	2θ (Calcd.)	$\Delta 2\theta$	($h k l$)
1	5.9430	5.9430	14.89	14.89	0.00	0 1 0
2	4.9420	4.9420	17.93	17.93	0.00	-1 1 0
3	4.4190	4.4190	20.08	20.08	0.00	0 -1 1
4	4.3620	4.3620	20.34	20.34	0.00	1 1 0
5	4.1640	4.1640	21.32	21.32	0.00	1 0 1
6	3.9190	3.9190	22.67	22.67	0.00	0 1 1
7	3.7900	3.8249	23.45	23.24	0.21	-1 1 1
8	3.4620	3.4337	25.71	25.93	-0.22	-2 0 1
9	3.1780	3.1823	28.05	28.02	0.03	1 1 1
10	3.0640	3.0835	29.85	29.86	-0.01	1 4 3
11	3.0120	3.0163	29.64	29.39	0.25	-2 1 1
12	2.9220	2.9137	30.57	30.66	-0.09	-2-1 1
13	2.7220	2.7338	32.88	32.73	0.15	0 -1 2
14	2.6370	2.6416	33.97	33.91	0.06	1 2 0
15	2.5320	2.5353	35.42	35.38	0.04	-2 0 2
16	2.4600	2.4603	36.50	36.49	0.01	1 -1 2
17	2.3260	2.3221	38.68	38.75	-0.07	-3 1 1
18	2.1160	2.1131	42.70	42.76	-0.06	3 0 1
19	2.0760	2.0820	43.56	43.43	0.13	2 0 2

shows sharp peaks indicating its crystalline nature. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the complex with respect to their prominent peaks have been indexed by using appropriate methodology and use of computer program (Powd Mult, Version 2.3). The above index method also yielded miller indices (h, k, l) values, unit cell parameters and volume of unit cell. The indexing is confirmed on the basis of correction obtained between observed and calculated values. The 2θ values and relative intensities corresponding to the prominent peaks have been listed in Table 4. The unit cell lattice parameter of VO^{IV} complex are $a = 7.5593 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 6.0199 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 5.9357 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 95.557^\circ$, $\beta = 100.824^\circ$, $\gamma = 96.086^\circ$, $V = 261.92 \text{ \AA}^3$. The system is therefore, triclinic in nature.

Biological activity :

In antibacterial study, the inhibition effects of the synthesize compounds on the growth of various microorganisms are listed in Table 5. Minimum inhibitory concentrations of these compounds were determined by literature method³². The results for antibacterial study are interpreted by measuring the zones of inhibition of growth of the bacterial culture. The results show that ligand H₂L

Table 5. Biological activity of compounds

Sr. no.	Ligand/Complex	Antibacterial activity (mm)			
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. abony</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>
1.	H ₂ L	12.66	12.54	12.86	12.64
2.	[VOL].H ₂ O	13.58	12.56	15.44	15.60
3.	[CrL.H ₂ O.Cl].H ₂ O	15.52	14.66	13.88	12.42
4.	[MnL.OAc]	14.36	14.24	13.30	13.40
5.	[FeL.H ₂ O.Cl].H ₂ O	16.62	12.77	17.10	14.95

and VO^{IV}, Cr^{III}, Mn^{III}, Fe^{III} complexes exhibit bacteriostatic behavior towards all the bacterial strain using in method. The VO^{IV}, Cr^{III}, Mn^{III} complexes were found to be show moderate bactericidal nature against all bacterial strains. This may be due to the less permeation through the lipid membrane in VO^{IV}, Cr^{III}, Mn^{III} complexes and thus moderate activity of these complexes. The Fe^{III} complex is found to show good activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, whereas moderate activity against the *S. abony* and *B. subtilis*. In general the results reveal that, the activity of the ligand was found to be enhanced on complexation with metal ions. It has been oftended that the metal complexes show enhanced antibacterial activity as compared to the free ligand against. The same microor-

ganism under identical experimental conditions, this is due to complexation³³. This may be explained by chelation theory, according to which chelation or complexation reduces the polarity of central metal atom because of partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor group within the whole chelate ring system. This chelation increases the lipophilic nature of the central atom, which favour the permeation of the complexes through the lipid layer of the cell membrane and results in enhancement of activity.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents were used of analytical grade and purchased from various commercial sources. Vanadyl sulphate pentahydrate, chromium chloride hexahydrate, anhydrous ferric chloride, dioxotungsten tetrathiocyanate, zirconium acetate, uranyl nitrate hexahydrate and carbonylhydrazide were of Rankem and SD's fine chemicals and use as supplied. $Mn(OAc)_3 \cdot 2H_2O$ was prepared by the oxidation of $Mn(OAc)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ using Christensen's method³⁴ and bis(acetylacetonato)-dioxomolybdenum(VI) were synthesized according to literature method³⁵.

Synthesis of N''-[1-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)ethylidene]-N'''-[1-(2-hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitrophenyl)ethylidene]carbonohydrazide (H₂L) :

The ligand H₂L was prepared by literature method^{36,37}. An ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone (2.4 g, 0.016 M) was mixed with ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitroacetophenone (3.12 g, 0.016 M) and to this mixture a hot ethanol-DMF solution (60 : 40 v/v; 25 ml) of carbonylhydrazide (1.44 g, 0.016 M) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The resulting mixture was refluxed on sand bath for about 8 h. The solvent was then partially evaporated under air and faint yellow coloured compound formed was suction filtered, washed with ethanol, petroleum ether and then dried *in vacuo*. Yield : 69%, m.p. 312 °C; 12.58 (1H, s, OH, phenolic), 12.44 (1H, s, OH, phenolic), 10.16 (1H, s, imino, NH), 10.11 (1H, s, imino, NH), 2.33 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.38 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.43 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.59 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.85–7.77 (5H, m, aryl-H).

The schematic representation of the synthesis of ligand H₂L is shown in Fig. 1.

Synthesis of VO^{IV}, Cr^{III}, Mn^{III}, Fe^{III}, MoO₂^{VI}, Zr^{IV} and UO₂^{VI} complexes :

To a hot DMF solution (25 ml) of the organic ligand (1.0 mmol), a hot ethanolic solution of the appropriate metal salt (1.0 mmol) solution was added under continuous stirring. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 4–5 h. On cooling to room temperature the precipitate solid metal complexes was filtered, washed thoroughly with ethanol, DMF and petroleum ether to remove unreacted ligand and metal salts. Finally all complexes dried under vacuum at room temperature, yield : 65–70%.

Synthesis of WO₂^{VI} complexes :

Sodium tungstate dihydrate (1.2 g, 0.00363 M) and ammonium thiocyanate (2.9 g, 0.038 M) were dissolved in water (30 ml) at room temperature and 7.5 ml of 11 M HCl was added to it. The resulting yellow solution was cooled in an ice bath and DMF solution (10 ml) of ligand (0.00363 M) was added to it. The precipitate so formed were filtered under suction, washed 3–4 times with water containing few drops of HCl and dried *in vacuo*.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analysis carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were obtained using Carlo Erba 1108 analyser in micro analytical laboratory, CDRI, Lucknow. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 597 spectrophotometer using KBr pallets at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh. ¹H NMR spectrum of ligand was obtained using a Bruker Avance-II 400 NMR spectrophotometer in a mixed solvent (DMSO + CdCl₂) at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on Varian SE UV-NIR spectrophotometer at RSIC, IIT, Chennai using MgO as reference. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by Gouy's method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as a calibrant and the diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants. The solid state d.c. electrical conductivity of compounds was measured by Zentech Electrometer in their compressed pellet form over 313–403 K temperature range. TG analysis of the complexes was carried out on Perkin-Elmer TG-2 thermobalance in ambient air with a heating rate of 10 °C per minute. Metal contents of the complexes were analysed gravimetrically after decomposing the complexes with a mixture of HClO₄, H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ and then igniting to metal oxide. The XRD measurement of the

complexes was recorded with a Bruker AXS, D8-ADVANCE (Gmbh, Karlsruhe, West Germany) equipped with θ/θ goniometer and a Lynx Eye detector. Gas chromatography was recorded using a Shimadzu 14B gas chromatography with SE-30 column and FID detector at School of Chemical Science, Devi Ahilya University, Indore. Biological activities of the ligand and its some complexes were carried out against the bacteria *E. coli*, *S. abony*, *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* by the agar well diffusion method.

Biological activity :

The antibacterial activity of ligand H_2L and VO^{IV} , Cr^{III} , Mn^{III} , Fe^{III} complexes were tested for their effect on the growth of microbial cultures. The antimicrobial activity has been evaluated by agar well diffusion method³⁸ using *E. coli*, *S. abony*, *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus* microorganisms. The concentration of compounds used for testing was 1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in DMSO and used as control. In a typical procedure a well was made on the agar medium incubated with microorganisms. The well was filled with the test solution using a micropipette and the plate was incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. During this period the test solution diffused and the growth of microorganisms was affected. The antibacterial activity of compound was evaluated by studying the growth inhibition against test microorganisms. The procedure was performed in separate plates for each microorganism.

Oxidation of styrene :

The catalytic oxidation of styrene with VO^{IV} and Mn^{III} complexes was studied. The catalytic reactions were carried out in 250 ml reaction flask fitted with water condenser. A common procedure was used for all reactions. In reactions styrene (1.04 g, 10 mmol) and 30% H_2O_2 (2.27 g, 20 mmol) were mixed in 10 ml of MeCN and the reaction mixture was heated at in an oil bath with continuous stirring at 80 °C for 8 h. The catalyst to be tested (0.020 g) was added to reaction mixture and reaction was considered to begin. The reaction was monitored at various time periods and checked by the gas chromatography. The effect of an amount of the catalyst was studied to obtained suitable reaction conditions.

Conclusion :

Based on the physicochemical and spectral data discussed above square pyramidal structure for Mn^{III} and VO^{IV} complexes, pentagonal bipyramidal geometry to Zr^{IV}

complex whereas octahedral geometry for Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} , MoO_2^{VI} , WO_2^{VI} and UO_2^{VI} complexes are proposed. It is assumed that the ligand behaves as dibasic ONNO tetradentate, coordinating via phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atoms as illustrate in Fig. 1. Thermal study revealed that complexes are thermally stable. The solid-state electrical conductivity of complexes increases with increase in temperature and suggested semi-conducting behavior. An XRD study suggested the triclinic crystal system to VO^{IV} complex. The catalytic conversions of styrene suggest that it increases with increase in amount of catalyst in presence of fixed amount of H_2O_2 and styrene. The complexes are biologically active and showed enhanced antimicrobial activities compared to the free ligand.

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